

br), 650 (m, br), 605 (w), 580 (m) and 520 (s) cm^{-1} arising from different modes of phenyl ring, thiohydrazide group and phenolic OH group vibrations. A broad and strong band at 1575 cm^{-1} can be attributed to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C}) + \delta\text{NH}_2$ vibration of thiohydrazide group^{15,16} which shifts to higher frequencies by 5-10 cm^{-1} . The symmetric (NH_2) deformation vibration of phpthH (at 1225 cm^{-1}) shifts to higher frequencies by 15-35 cm^{-1} in complexes, indicating the co-ordination of hydrazine part terminal nitrogen with metal atom^{15,16}.

Thioamide bands I, II and III located at 1548, 1280 and 1012 cm^{-1} are also shifted to higher frequencies by 10-90 cm^{-1} while thioamide band IV (730 cm^{-1}) shifts to lower frequencies by 10-50 cm^{-1} in its complexes on coordination^{16,17}. Thus, from the study of the ir spectra of the ligand and its complexes, it is inferred that thioamide sulphur and thiohydrazide part terminal nitrogen are involved in coordination¹⁷. In far infrared region, the complexes display two to three new bands between 450 and 320 cm^{-1} region. The ir band located at 450-400 cm^{-1} is assigned to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ and between 350 and 320 cm^{-1} to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{S})$ vibrations^{18,19}.

References

1. U. KUMARI, C. P. SINGH and L. K. MISHRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 255.
2. B. N. KESHARI and L. K. MISHRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 1149; *Indian J. Chem.*, 1981, **20A**, 883.
3. L. K. MISHRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 1198.
4. J. R. DYLWONTH, J. H. P. VELLA, VENKAT SUBRAMANAM and JON A. ZUBEETA, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1979, **18**, 268.
5. E. LARSEN, P. TRINDERUP, B. OLSEN and K. J. WATSON, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1970, **24**, 261.
6. J. GABEL, E. LARSEN and P. TRINDRUP, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1977, **A31**, 657.
7. F. HANSEN and S. LARSEN, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1977, **A31**, 825.
8. K. A. JENSEN and C. PEDERSEN, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1961, **15**, 1097.
9. M. KATO, N. JONASSEN and J. C. FANNING, *Chem. Rev.*, 1964, **64**, 99.
10. W. MANCH and W. C. FERNELIUS, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1961, **38**, 192.
11. G. PEYRONEL, G. C. PELLACANI and A. PIGNEDOLI, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1971, **5**, 627.
12. F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry, A Comprehensive Text", Interscience Publisher, Inc., New York, 1966, p. 610, 621.
13. A. ALBERT and E. SPINNER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 1221, 1237.
14. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 1963, p. 197.
15. R. G. BURNS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, **7**, 277.
16. C. N. R. RAO, R. VENKATARAGHAWAN and T. R. KASTURI, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1964, **82**, 36.
17. T. SUZUKI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1962, **35**, 1286, 1449, 1456.
18. D. M. ADAMS and J. B. GORNELL, *J. Chem. Soc. A*, 1968, 1299.
19. M. AKBAR ALI, S. E. LIVINGSTONE and B. J. PHILLIPS, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1971, **5**, 119, 493.

Dehydration-Rehydration Behaviour of Zirconium and Thorium Hydroxide Hydrogel in Relation to Temperature of Heat Treatment

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THE hydroxide hydrogels of zirconium and thorium can be prepared in various ways¹⁻⁴ and the resultant products also differ in their physico-chemical characteristics. These gel materials are very important for studying many high temperature reactions. Hydrous zirconia shows signs of crystallinity⁵ with increase in drying temperature as evidenced by X-ray analysis. Precipitated amorphous zirconia inverts to tetragonal ZrO_2 at 400°⁶ and monoclinic at 600-800°⁷. With this inversion all identity as hydrous zirconia disappears but traces of water persists upto about 1000°⁸.

Maiti *et al*⁹ observed that the transition temperature of phase changes increases with increase in crystallite size. Considering the importance of hydroxide gels of tetravalent cations such as Zr^{4+} and Th^{4+} the study of the flexibility of dehydration-rehydration was undertaken. In this part heat treatment was carried out under equilibrium condition upto 900°.

Experimental

Hydrogels of zirconium and thorium were prepared from acidic solutions of zirconium nitrate and thorium nitrate by interaction with $\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}-\text{NH}_4\text{OH}$ buffer at pH 9. After proper ageing they were processed in accordance with literature method¹⁰ to get rid of the extraneous impurities.

Equilibrium dehydration-rehydration was studied by following the procedure as adopted by Mitra *et al*¹¹.

Results and Discussion

The hydroxide gels of zirconium and thorium, as synthesised under present experimental conditions, were amorphous in nature as evidenced by X-ray analysis (Fig. not shown). The equilibrium dehydration curves were discontinuous in nature (Fig. 1). Both these hydrogels showed inflection, in the early stage due to removal of loosely bound water and at higher temperature due to expulsion of constitutional hydroxyl groups. The temperatures of inflection were comparatively high with thorium hydroxide gel. In case of thorium hydroxide gel the dehydration loss above 500° was not very significant (Fig. 1) whereas in case of zirconium hydroxide gel the hydroxyl groups are bonded with higher

Fig. 1. Effect of heat treatment on the dehydration characteristics and bulk density change of hydrogels.

energy and as such higher magnitude of thermal excitation was needed for their expulsion.

During progressive heat treatment both zirconium and thorium hydroxide gel undergo some low temperature phase transformation which might be the controlling factor for further dehydration. A comparison of the two curves indicated that zirconium hydroxide gel on heat treatment at 900° still retained some lattice water. Bulk density change was not fully analogous to the dehydration curves but significant discontinuity was observed (Fig. 1). In case of zirconium hydroxide gel bulk density initially increased upto 600° due to contraction of physical pores followed by a decrease upto 800°. The initial increase was also associated with the conversion into tetragonal form but above 600° the reduction of bulk density might be due to inversion into monoclinic form whose atomic packing was less dense. Stepwise change of bulk density change on progressive heat treatment was exhibited by thorium hydroxide gel. The last traces of water which was bonded with relatively high energy might be a factor for catalysing the interaction.

The rehydration curves (Figs. 2 and 3) were analogous to that of the corresponding dehydration curves. The nature of the curves was found to be independent of humidity. The magnitude of rehydration sharply decreased above 400° due to decrease of surface area by the process of crystallisation (Fig. 2). Similar inflection points were noticed with thorium hydroxide gel above 600°. The rehydration was calculated on the basis of the dehydrated weight.

The magnitude of rehydration was comparatively high with zirconium hydroxide gel.

Fig. 2. Rehydration characteristics of zirconium hydroxide gel on progressive heat treatment.

Fig. 3. Rehydration characteristics of thorium hydroxide gel on progressive heat treatment.

Conclusion :

1. Both zirconium and thorium hydroxide hydrogels showed discontinuous dehydration and rehydration curves. The magnitude of dehydration as well as the rehydration was comparatively high with zirconium hydroxide gel.

2. The change of bulk density on progressive heat treatment indicated that some phase transformation other than dehydration also occurred in this process.

3. The rehydration curves were analogous to that of the dehydration curves.

References

1. C. B. AMPLETT, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1958, 6, 17.
2. H. TH. RIJNTEN, "Physical and Chemical Aspects of Adsorbents and Catalysts", (Ed.) B. G. LINSSEN, Academic Press, 1970, p. 315
3. "Encyclopedia of Chemical Technology", Interscience Publishers, John Wiley and Sons, Inc., New York, London, 1969, Vol. 20.

NOTES

4. K. H. McCORKLE, A. T. KLEINSTENBER, C. E. SCHILLING and D. C. DEAN, *U. S. Pat.*, 3,036, 896, May 22, 1962.
5. N. MICHAEL, W. D. FLITCHER *et al*, Westinghouse Report CVNA-135, 1961.
6. J. LIVAGE, *Bull. Soc. Chim. France*, 1968, 2, 507.
7. A. G. BOGANOV, V. S. RUDDENKO and L. P. MAKAROV, *Dokl. Akad. Nauk. USSR*, 1965, 58, 160, 1065.
8. E. CRUCEAN and B. RAND, *Trans. Brit. Ceramic Soc.*, 1979, 78.
9. H. S. MAITI, K. V. G. K. GOKHALE and E. C. SUBBARAO, *J. Amer. Ceram. Soc.*, 1972, 55, 317.
10. N. K. MITRA and K. L. ROY, *Trans. Ind. Ceram. Soc.*, 1972, 31, 82.
11. N. K. MITRA, S. GHATAK and S. MITRA, *Trans. Brit. Ceram. Soc.*, 1977, 76, 6.

Viscosity of Sr(NO₃)₂ and Cd(NO₃)₂ in Mixed Solvents at Different Temperatures

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WATER at ordinary temperature has a quasicrystalline structure. A dynamic equilibrium seems to exist between the three dimensional hydrogen bonded clusters and the denser monomers: (H₂O)_c ⇌ (H₂O)_a. Electrolytes dissolving in water has been classified as structure makers or structure breakers, depending on whether the above equilibrium shifts to the left or to the right. Ions with a lower charge density has a smaller width of region-A in which it is surrounded by concentric region of water molecules, analogous to a kind of freezing and a larger width of region-B, which has got the tendency to resist the normal three dimensional water structure called region-C, and the balance between the two competing forces are net structure breakers. On the other hand, ions with high charge density show an opposite behaviour and are net structure makers¹.

Organic solvents like dioxane, glycol and methyl alcohol are miscible with water at all solvent compositions and their dielectric constants and dipole moments are very different. Dioxane, glycol and methyl alcohol are aprotic solvents, whereas water is both an electron donor and an acceptor. Hence, studies of their aqueous mixtures become an interesting field to explore, particularly of the ionic processes accompanying the solutions of strong electrolytes.

From this point of view, the viscosity of the solutions of Sr(NO₃)₂ and Cd(NO₃)₂ at 10, 20 and 30 weight % of dioxane, glycol and methyl alcohol

have been measured at concentrations, C ≤ 0.1 mol.l⁻¹ at 30 to 45° for dioxane+water and glycol+water and at 30 to 40 ± 0.01° for methyl alcohol+water mixtures.

Experimental

All salts used were of E. Merck, 'extra pure' grade. The contents were estimated in the usual manner. The preparation of the solvents, solutions and viscometric technique were the same as those of Das². The densities of the solutions and the solvents were determined by pycnometer with buoyancy correction and the method is the same as that of Das³. All precautions were taken to check the evaporation of the solvents⁴. The time of flow for each concentration did not exceed by 0.2 sec in about 15 min. Density readings were precise upto 0.0002 g/cm³, i.e. an error of 4 in 10⁶. The concentration range was from 0.1 to 0.001 mol.l⁻¹.

Results and Discussion

Viscosity of the mixed solvents as well as those of the salt solutions under study was measured and the results have been analysed. The Jones-Dole⁵ equation $\eta_r = 1 + A\sqrt{C} + BC$ is found to be valid as the plot of $\eta_r - 1/C^{1/2}$ vs $C^{1/2}$ is linear. The intercept and the slope gave respectively the coefficient A and B. The values of A and B, thus obtained, are given in Tables 1 and 2, respectively.

'A' values : The difference of 'A' values (Table 1) indicates dependence of ionic interaction on the nature of the electrolyte and are all positive. The electrostatic ion-ion interaction and hence the value of 'A' is found to increase with decrease in dielectric constant, i.e. when the concentration of the organic solvent increase. It is seen from Table 1 that the ion-ion interaction is of the order Cd²⁺ > Sr²⁺. Further, the value of 'A' decreases with increase in temperature, which one should expect (excepting glycol) in view of the greater thermal agitation at higher temperature and reduction of attractive forces. This, however, is not happening in case of glycol+water as the mixture is more viscous.

TABLE 1
A × 10³/l^{1/2}.mol^{1/2}
Weight % of

Temp. °C	Dioxane			Glycol			Methanol		
	10	20	30	10	20	30	10	20	30
Sr(NO ₃) ₂									
30	10.4	10.9	11.0	14.4	15.2	16.3	9.3	10.1	10.6
35	10.6	10.7	11.8	14.5	15.1	16.2	9.1	9.9	10.4
40	10.4	10.5	11.6	14.6	15.4	16.3	8.8	9.7	10.1
45	10.8	10.3	11.4	14.5	15.6	16.4			
Cd(NO ₃) ₂									
30	12.1	12.6	13.2	16.2	17.2	18.4	10.4	11.2	11.6
35	12.0	12.4	13.0	16.1	17.0	18.3	10.2	10.9	11.4
40	11.8	12.2	12.8	16.0	17.1	18.1	10.0	10.7	11.2
45	11.6	12.0	12.6	16.2	17.2	18.2			

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